

Protection of Child Rights - The Role of Media

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Extensive Media coverage on Nithari case (2006) where innocent children were abused and brutally killed and buried, the famous Arushi and Hemraj double murder case (2008) a case of suspected honor killing, and the case of brutal rape of a 5-year-old girl in Delhi. These and many others like dismal status of children living in shelter home etc gathered tremendous media attention and somewhere very boldly questioned accountability of the decision makers. Media and Communication systems is increasing becoming central areas of profit making in today's modern capitalist societies. I think 24*7 news channels certainly holds all capacities to mesmerize and influences the thought pattern of masses to such an extent that one might get filled with empathy by looking at sadden faces, abandoned children and shock struck individuals giving media bytes to innumerable humming media channel personnel. When I look at coverage of child rights issues in our county, I am of an opinion that not all the news channels and newspaper practice 'responsible' journalism/reporting. Merely by not naming and blurring the picture or giving her a pseudo name does not ensure communication the right 'news' to the viewers.

Need and significance of the study:

It is important that the media themselves do not abuse children. The integrity of the child should be protected in reporting about, for instance, involvement in criminal activities, sexual abuse and family problems. Fortunately, the media in some countries have voluntarily agreed to respect guidelines which offer such protection of the privacy of the

ABSTRACT

"All children have rights and those rights must be protected"

- Novak Djokovic

Media plays a crucial role in society. They act as the eyes, ears and voices of the public, drawing attention to abuses of power and human rights, often at considerable personal risk. Through their work they can encourage governments and civil society organizations to effect changes that will improve the quality of people's lives. Media also helps in bringing awareness and of course protecting the rights of every child irrespective of their background. The present paper is an overview to investigate the role of media in addressing rights of the child. To achieve this following objectives were framed followed by research questions, i. To identify the role of media in addressing the child rights issues, ii. To develop awareness in the civil society regarding protection of child rights. The author gave necessary suggestions to empower children.

Keywords: child rights, protection, juvenile delinquency and media

INTRODUCTION

There is no debate that there are many examples of 'good' journalism in the recent past which has generated mass awareness around issues pertaining to child rights especially child protection. In the recent past there has been

child; however, such ethical standards are not always adhered to. The Convention on the Rights of the Child is formally addressed to Governments and does not interfere with the independence of the media; however, it does have an indirect message for media institutions: as with human rights in general, the press and other media have essential functions in promoting and protecting the fundamental rights of the child.

Operational terms defined:

1. **Child rights:** are the human rights of children with particular attention to the rights of special protection and care afforded to minors.
2. **Protection:** the action of protecting, or the state of being protected.
3. **Juvenile delinquency:** the habitual committing of criminal acts or offences by a young person, especially one below the age at which ordinary criminal prosecution is possible.
4. **Media:** the main means of mass communication (broadcasting, publishing, and the Internet) regarded collectively.

Objectives:

1. To identify the role of media in addressing the child rights issues.
2. To develop awareness in the civil society regarding protection of child rights.
3. To suggest media to sustain serious attempt in protecting children rights.
4. To mould public opinion regarding mass media.

Research questions:

1. What is the importance of media in protecting child rights?
2. Whether there is a need of protection of child rights in civil society?

Details of the study:

India is home to the world's largest child population. It also has over three million civil society organisations (csos) and one of the largest and most complex media landscapes in the world. A signatory to the Convention of the Rights of the Child, India has introduced several path-breaking programmes and legislations for safeguarding child rights. However, a low budgetary investment toward children has meant severe gaps in execution.

The Committee on the Rights of the Child believes that the media - both written and audiovisual - are highly important in the efforts to make reality the principles and standards of the Convention. The media in many countries have already contributed greatly in creating an awareness of the Convention and its content.

The media could also play a pivotal role in monitoring the actual implementation of the rights of the child. In their reporting the media give an "image" of the child; they reflect and influence perceptions about who children are and how they behave. This image could create and convey respect for young people; however, it could also spread prejudices and stereotypes which may have a negative influence on public opinion and politicians. Nuanced and well-informed reporting is to the benefit of the rights of the child.

It is important that the media themselves do not abuse children. The integrity of the child should be protected in reporting about, for instance, involvement in criminal activities, sexual abuse and family problems. Fortunately, the media in some countries have voluntarily agreed to respect guidelines which offer such protection of the privacy of the child; however, such ethical standards are not always adhered to.

Concern has also been expressed about the influence on children of negative aspects of the media, primarily programmes containing brutal violence and pornography. There is discussion in a number of countries about how to protect children from violence on television in video films and in other modern media. Again, voluntary agreements have been attempted, with varied impact. This particular problem is raised in article 17 of the Convention which

recommends that appropriate guidelines be developed "for the protection of the child from information and material injurious to his or her well-being".

Table 1: Indian media and access to consumers

Media platform	Consumers in India (millions)	% Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) ¹⁹	Media credibility ranking ²⁰
Mobile (subscribers)	900 ²¹	n.a.	n.a.
Television (viewers)	730 ²²	5.2	2
Print (readers)	353 ²³	0.8	1
Radio (listeners)	159 ²⁴	1.9	3
Internet (users)	124 ²⁵	24.2	4

Journalists need to be aware of the consequences of their reporting. The co-operation of media organizations and journalist and their orientation towards safeguarding the rights and the dignity of children and young adults is extremely important for all who strive for wider recognition of children's rights.

Suggestion:

Reporting and covering child protection issues is not merely covering a sensational news piece but it goes much beyond that. It is an act of bringing the issue of child rights and child protection in public debate and policy discourse and thus resulting in serious effort to capture the route followed to avail justice.

The issue of bringing about mass awareness around child right is a serious sustained commitment and political will. We house millions of children in our country who are malnourished, live in extremely unprotected environment, who are often abused in and are engaged in labor instead of spending their childhood in school.

There is serious challenge for modern day Media to responsibly keep taking up child rights issue and keep them alive in public discourse.

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